

COVERT (INSTITUTIONAL) DISCRIMINATION

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The Article 14 of European Convention on Human Rights prohibits discrimination on any ground such as sex, race, color, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, association with a national minority, property, birth, or other status. The list of protected grounds is not exhaustive. Restrictions of basic human rights and freedoms are legitimate only if all of three parts of the test are met:

1. The interference must be provided for by the law.
2. The interference must pursue a legitimate aim.
3. The restriction must be necessary in democratic society, adequate and proportionate.

Therefore, restriction of human rights and freedoms, such as in COVID-19 pandemic, should be proportional to the objective threat, it should be provided for by the law, it should pursue a legitimate aim, such as a better control of the pandemic, but also the assistance provided by the government for every citizen in need must be proportional to the justified restriction of human liberties.

One might argue that the restrictions made by the governments in COVID-19 pandemic did not meet all the three parts of the test (legality, legitimate aim, necessity-adequacy-proportionality), especially when it comes to restrictions based on COVID-19 vaccination status, which might be understood as one of the protected grounds, based on which no one should be discriminated against. The COVID-19 passports, one might argue, can be understood as a form of covert, institutional discrimination, in which such discrimination is made (quasi) legal, and no one can file a case against it. It is quite vague whether COVID-19 vaccination status-based restrictions of basic human rights and freedoms really passed the three parts of the test or not, and whether the COVID-19 passports were an actual legal document, or just another marketing trick.

In some cases, COVID-19 vaccination status might be only a decoy for the discrimination based on some other ground, such as different political views. For example, an employer with liberal political views does not want to hire a candidate with conservative political views (discrimination

based on different political views), despite being the best candidate, and uses the COVID-19 vaccination status as a decoy and (quasi) legal excuse for rejecting this candidate.

The iceberg of covert (institutional) discrimination may consist of:

1. The most visible part: administrative illogicalities, irregularities, and obstacles, such as the requirement of COVID-19 vaccination certificate in cases in which this was not made legally obligatory (non-existence of real legal obligation, but it is rather arbitrarily required by individual organization and/or employer in order to obtain the right for employment or participation in certain social activities).
2. Decoy: COVID-19 vaccination status (especially if such status has not been made legally obligatory, but it is arbitrarily required by individual organization and/or employer).
3. The real (hidden) reason: discrimination based on one or more protected grounds, usually different political views, gender, sexual orientation, race, nationality, socio-economic status...

Figure: The iceberg of covert (institutional) discrimination

To conclude, the covert (institutional) discrimination may be prevented with:

1. High quality legislation that is in conformity with international human rights standards and in the case of restrictions, strictly follows, all of the three parts of the test.
2. Simple, transparent, and user-friendly administrative obligations that are provided by the law, and not arbitrarily determined by individual organization and/or employer.
3. Constantly promoting anti-discrimination policies and raising awareness of potential detrimental social and health effects of covert (institutional) discrimination.